

Combining Volunteered Geographic Information and WPdx standards to Improve Mapping of Rural Water Infrastructure in Uganda

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Access to clean and safe drinking water is critical to public health and socioeconomic prosperity, yet an estimated quarter of the world's population lacks such [1]. This was evidenced by the unprecedented outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic, which left communities extremely vulnerable to fatal illnesses due to the limited access to water for handwashing or lack of knowledge of the existence of the utility [2].

Subsequently, the lack of data on the distribution of drinking water resources poses a great challenge to optimizing water resource investments and has limited Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning-enabled advancements in the water sector compared to all other sectors like health [3]. Increasing the frequency of water point data collection and sharing through crowdsourcing and volunteered geographic information would greatly improve the availability of water point data, and contribute to the extended roles of water resource distribution, monitoring, and management, especially in rural communities. Therefore, this paper describes the methodology for combining different water mapping schemas to create comprehensive multi-platform drinking water infrastructure data and enhance rapid updates to support a suite of drinking water resource analytics, and extended advanced technology explorations towards improved decision-making.

Through the water infrastructure mapping project in Gulu, Uganda, a comprehensive OpenStreetMap (OSM) water tag review was conducted to explicitly maximize the usage and application of these crowdsourced data in the Water Point Data Exchange (WPdx) [4] suite of analytical platforms for sharing, access and using data to improve decision making in the Water, Sanitation and Hygiene sector. A relative data model resulting from a region-specific knowledge landscape was developed to facilitate the

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mapping of water infrastructure data points, and simultaneous updates of both the WPdx & OSM databases, through mobile data collection. Underlying the development of this data model/schema, a design criterion was established which guided and justified the overall selection of the most relevant factors to include in the process that would eventually become detailed to communicate water infrastructure and functionality for administrative decision support. The criteria were followed by an assessment of the compliance, consistency, completeness, and granularity [5] of the OSM tag to support the development of the OSM language in the Kobo toolbox [6]. A field mapping workflow was designed to facilitate the field-data collection employing the developed water infrastructure data model and Kobo toolbox.

More than 15,000 buildings, 1,400 km² of roads and over 500 water data points were added to OSM as well as the WPdx database for the later data. In addition, observations were made regarding the improvement of such processes and potential extension of such methods beyond one geographical area.

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